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AN INTRODUCTION OF ISLAMIC ECONOMY AND ITS EFFECTS ON GLOBAL ECONOMY

Saeid Michaghani

Research Scholar of Theology, Aligarh Muslim University, India

ABSTRACT

Theories on economic development stipulate is the key role that technology plays in ensuring growth in countries' GDP. Considering the classical approach to economic growth, that is, increased output in the economy in the long run is entirely dependent on the velocity of money, the price level, money supply and the number of transactions in the aggregate economy. The velocity of money, in terms of the number of times a unit of currency can be used in a transaction, is the most important parameter in this instance. An increase in the velocity of money most definitely increases the economic growth of states through its impact on the classical model on economic growth. It is therefore very necessary to concentrate on the ways of increasing money Islamic financial institutions are expected to provide special services to those in need. This is not confined to mere charitable donations but has also been institutionalized in the industry in the form of profit-free loans or Al Quard Al Hasanah. Islamic Economic provides profit-free loans. For example, if there is an individual needs to go to hospital or wants to go to university, without any profit, this system will provide facility.

In this article I try to introduce briefly Islamic Economy according to secondary data, and the research methodology of this article would be content analysis.

Key Words: Al Quard Al Hasanah, Global Economy, Economy, Islamic Economy, Shariah.

I. Introduction

A frequently discussed issue in the Islamic economy is the shortage of Shari'ah scholars and the need for a global infrastructure to fill this gap within the framework of some recognized standards (Greuning and Iqbal, 2008; Hamzah, 2010). Despite pronounced resistance from some senior scholars, the recent initiative by the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI) to set a new standard for Shari'ah scholars underscores the concern (The Peninsula, 2010; El Baltaji, 2010; El Baltaji and Anwar, 2010; New Horizon, 2011).

This is indeed a formidable challenge, but experience with the industry gives us new insight on how the required human resources and talents can be developed within the presently available infrastructure.

Currently, the global financial system is gradually embracing Islamic economy as one of its definitive segments. While there are many institutions, including international organizations, such as Thomson Reuters, Deloitte Touche, Moody's and Bloomberg, that are recognizing the importance of this segment and mobilizing more resources to support Islamic economic initiatives, the 'privilege' of Islamic finance extends only to the communities that can afford its high Shari'ah-compliance premium (Shufelt, 2010). It is widely recognized that there are hurdles other than affordability and cost that remain significant bottlenecks for the industry's growth. These include lack of wider and cheaper distribution channels, standardized products and higher volumes and liquidity. In addition, the credibility of Islamic economic continues to be a problem with the common Muslims, especially due to skepticism regarding the core Shari'ah-compliance process (El Gamal, 2005; Remo-Listana,

2009; Ahmed, 2010; Muto, 2010).

For Islamic economic to move to the mainstream and really serve the man on the street, it must resolve, among other matters, issues of efficiency and credibility associated with the Shari'ah-compliance standards and process, which threaten to place the entire Islamic economy industry at risk. The potential downside, if the industry and its gatekeepers, the Shari'ah scholars, do not resolve these challenges, is significant. One negative repercussion would be regulatory capture and the other would be loss of legitimacy in the eyes of its primary customers: the Muslims.

As Shari'ah governance is at the core of Islamic economy, a related and pivotal challenge is the education and training of Shari'ah scholars in the context of the complexity, dynamism and interrelatedness of our contemporary world, so that the qualifications are duly standardized. This paper specifically discusses this challenge facing the Islamic economy industry and looks into possible long-term solutions to address the issue of the qualification and training of Shari'ah scholars.

II. Islamic Economy

While Islamic economy responds to the needs of Muslim customers, they are not acting as religious institutions. Like other banks they are profit-maximizing entities. They act as intermediaries between savers and investors and offer custodial and other services found in traditional banking systems. The constraints facing Islamic economy are, however, different. They are based on prescriptions in Shariah law, which encompasses a set of duties that also apply to commercial transactions, and the hadith—the authentic traditions. Islamic law affects how the banking system functions. Four factors in particular are unique to Islamic banking. We summarize them here briefly (for a good exposition, see El-Gamal (2006).

III. Benefits of Islamic Economy

Prohibition of interest (*Riba*). Riba is the major difference between Islamic and traditional economy. Islam prohibits all forms of riba (interest paid on loans) on the grounds that interest rates are a form of exploitation, inconsistent with the notion of fairness. Practically, this implies that Shariah law does not allow fixing in advance a positive return on a loan as a reward for waiting. The argument is that riba implies an improper appropriation of other people's property and is bad for growth. Islam does recognize the importance of the time value of money, but the time value is not realized as part of a loan contract; it can be realized only as part of a real transaction. For example, in a leasing agreement, the time value of money is an integral part of the rent to which the parties agree, with longer leases expected to yield higher returns. Prohibition of *maysir* (games of chance) and of *gharar* (chance). Islamic economy bans speculation, which is increasing one's wealth by chance rather than productive effort. In practice, though, the distinction between speculation and productive effort is often blurred. While entrepreneurship itself could be interpreted as a form of gambling, maysir refers to unnecessary uncertainties not part of everyday life, such as going to a casino. Unavoidable risk is permitted.

A related concept is the prohibition of gharar contracts. It applies to doubtful or uncertain contracts, such as undertaking a business venture without sufficient information or taking excessive risk. It is similar to asymmetric information; the objective is to minimize possibilities of misunderstanding and conflicts between contracting parties.

Prohibition of *haram* (illegal) activities. The code of conduct for Islamic economy allows them to finance only *halal* (legal) activities. They are not supposed to lend to companies or individuals involved in activities deemed to have a negative impact on society (for example, gambling) or that are illegal under Islamic law (for example, financing construction of a plant to make alcoholic beverages).

Payment of part of bank profits to benefit society (*zakat*). Muslims believe that justice and equality in opportunity (not outcome) are crucial for a society to function. One mechanism to achieve this goal is to

redistribute income to provide a minimum standard of living for the poor. This form of giving, zakat, is also one of the five tenets of Islam. It is generally agreed that the amount of zakat is 2.5 percent of assets held. In countries where zakat is not collected by the state, Islamic banks establish a zakat fund for collecting money to be donated to religious institutions.

Given these characteristics, would Islamic economy be good for growth? The analysis by Bhalla (2002) revealed that in comparison to the worldwide mean, Islamic countries are poor and not highly developed. Some scholars argue that Islam, by preaching fatalism, might negatively affect growth (Kuran, 1997). However, much of the evidence does not support this argument. First, the Golden Age of Islam between the 9th and 15th centuries, when advances were made in science, literature, navigation, law, and philosophy, illustrates that Islamic societies are capable of progress and innovation when the right environment is in place (Turner, 1997). More recently, Noland (2003), in an authoritative study, concludes that:

Predominantly Muslim countries are seldom outliers (either positively or negatively) in the cross-country regressions. In most cases, the coefficient on the Muslim population share is statistically insignificant. With one exception, where it is significant, it is always positive. The only case of a statistically significant negative coefficient is in the sub-national regression for Malaysia. Islam does not appear to be a drag on growth or an anchor on development as alleged. If anything, the opposite appears to be true. If one is concerned about economic performance in predominantly Muslim regions or countries, conventional economic analysis may yield greater insight than the sociology of religion.

In fact, not only does Islam not negatively impact growth, but Islamic economy could complement conventional banks and thereby help diversify systemic risk. In conventional banks, when a bank gives out a loan, the borrower bears all risks, except in the case of bankruptcy. In Islamic economy, both bank and entrepreneur share the rewards and failure. In many developing countries risk sharing might allow entrepreneurs with little savings to undertake projects they could not contemplate in an environment where all the risk lies on them. In conventional economy, the creditworthiness of the borrower is the main determinant of the lending decision, and banks are interested in the interest and principal on the loan. In Islamic economy, because profits and losses are shared, banks will receive a return only if a project is successful. Therefore, Islamic banks are more prone to finance sound projects, even if the entrepreneur has no credit history.

Figure1: Share of Islamic Banks in Total Banking System in Selected Countries, 2006

Sources: Bankscope and authors' calculations

If we compare credit by Islamic banks to the depth of the financial system, even in countries like Malaysia where Islamic banking is well-developed, it is dwarfed by conventional banks

Figure 2. Share of Credit by Islamic Banks in Total Banking Credit in Selected Countries (average 1992-2006)

Sources: Bankscope, Financial Development and Structure Database, and authors' calculations.

If we now measure the importance of Islamic economy in the economy by assets, we see that in almost all countries, except Iran, the ratio of credit of conventional banks to GDP is substantially higher than the investment to GDP ratio of Islamic banks, which accounts for less than 20 percent of GDP in most countries (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Comparing Investment by Islamic Banks with Credit by Conventional Banks in Selected Countries (average 1992-2006, percent of GDP)

Sources: Bankscope, Financial Development and Structure Database, and authors' calculations.

Therefore, the importance of Islamic banking varies, being high in the Gulf and East Asia in absolute numbers though relatively small in comparison with how much investment they finance as a share of GDP compared to conventional banks. In other regions, the importance of Islamic banking is even lower.

IV. Theory of Firm in Islamic Economics

Amin et al (2003) explained that in the Islamic framework, it is assumed that economic agents are guided by Islamic values. Thus, an Islamic producer, being accountable to Allah, treats the resources at his command as a trust and the production of goods as a duty, and he will base his production decisions on the concept of 'maslaha'. The author opines that a producer in an Islamic market could still be profit-driven; but, being governed by the Islamic principles, the producer's valuation of economic costs will be modified. Hence, the producer will internalize the externalities in its utility and cost functions. Discussing the goal of the firm in an Islamic economy, Hasan (2002) argued that it is important to understand what is being maximized, how, and for what purpose.

He cites examples and said that maximizing survival, employment, equity, or the pleasure of God would probably be welcome to most of the people. Hence, according to the author, maximizing behavior in Islamic economics is admissible. The author opines that if the firms fulfill their Islamic duties towards the consumers, the employees, and the society in general in arriving at their total revenue curves, then profit maximization is not objectionable. He argues for internalizing social costs and benefits. In mathematical modeling of a firm's behavior, Metwally (1997) describes an Islamic firm as one that would seek the maximization of utility which is a function of the amount of profits and the amount of spending on charity or good deeds. The author suggests using utility as a broad function which includes net profits as well as charity as parameters. However, the amount of profit would, after the payment of all imposed taxes (Zakat and other dues) be no less than a minimum level which is 'safe' to keep the firm in business. In another mathematical formulation, Bendjilali and Taher (1990) argue that even in imperfect market structure like a monopoly, if the monopolist is concerned about the social welfare, then he will be willing to partially sacrifice his profits in order to attain efficiency and minimize social welfare loss. Hence, it could be appreciated that several authors have emphasized on the ethical and spiritual rationality in the firm's behavior. In a value neutral framework, there is no cap or mechanism to solve problem of a human's greed. In fact, a value neutral framework provides a cover to follow, pursue, harness and practice greed. On the other hand, Islam addresses hearts and first of all, it purifies the heart, encourages compassion, responsibility and gives concepts of shared responsibility and afterlife accountability.

V. Research Methodology

This study is exploratory and analytical in nature. This study analyzes Islamic economics literature to clarify various charges of anomalies in the institution of Shariah. It takes into account quantitative data to estimate the potential of tax revenues by using the institution of Zakah and non-tax revenues using various other means available in an Islamic economy. It also gives an analytical appraisal of the proposed system in light of public finance literature.

VI. Suggestions

The Islamic financial system is based on equity whereas the conventional banking system is loan based. Islam is not against the earning of money. In fact, Islam prohibits earning of money through unfair trading practices and other activities that are socially harmful in one way or another. Those who swallow down usury cannot arise except as one whom SHAITAN (evil) has prostrated by (his) touch does rise. That is because they say, trading is only like usury; and Allah has allowed trading and forbidden usury. To whomsoever then the admonition has come from his Lord, then he desists, he shall have what has already passed, and his affair is in the hands of Allah; and whoever returns (to it) - these are the inmates of the fire; they shall abide in it [SURAH 2:275] .

Not that there was any ambiguity in the Command of Allah. Far be it from Him to give any order to His Servants, which they cannot comprehend. The fact is that those who had surplus money and wanted to earn profit did so either by lending it through RIBA (usury) or by investing it in trade and hypocrites were not prepared to forgo the first option. Hence, they argued that since both were means of earning profit, they were

alike and the prohibition of RIBA did not stand to reason.

The practice of RIBA i.e. usury was so deep-rooted in society and continuance of the practice was so undesirable, that Allah warned the believers that if they did not desist, they should be prepared for a war against Allah and His Apostle. This warning was heeded by the Muslim UMMAH and for more than a thousand years the economies of Muslim states were free from RIBA. With the ascendancy of Western influence and its suzerainty over Muslim states, the position changed and an interest-based economy became acceptable. Efforts in Muslim countries to revert to an interest-free economy were hampered by many obstacles.

VII. Conclusions

To outline the broad features of a strategy which holds the promise of successfully implementing an Islamic system of finance are as follows:

- The process has to be guided by basic legislative efforts covering all the essential elements of the proposed programmed.
- The legislation would define RIBA and prohibit transactions connected with RIBA.
- The application of the law would be unqualified and without exception, thus the entire financial sector, covering banking government finance and foreign transactions would be covered in its ambit.
- Given the unqualified and non-exceptional nature of the proposed law, even existing relations will have to be converted into permissible forms, for which a suitable time frame, within a phasing-in period, will be allowed.
- The law should also provide for the Constitution of a SHARIAH Board which would assist the SBP to formulate permissible means of financing. Such means, specified with the prior approval of the Board, will only be illustrative and no restrictions will be placed on banks and financial institutions to design means of financing which are free of RIBA.
- A major portion of the law will have to be devoted to a plan of restructuring the fiscal policy which comprises a scheme for the privatization of public sector assets and the use of its proceeds for the settlement of the outstanding stock of public debt .

The proposed strategy is based on the clear recognition of the scope implied by the prohibition of RIBA. This is critical, for otherwise the solution will continue to elude us.

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